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Research Article

PATIENT'S SATISFACTION WITH NEUROSURGERY OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT (OPD) SERVICES OF TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Abstract:

Background: Patient's satisfaction with services measures the quality of healthcare and needs to be addressed as it serves as proxy indicator of the future utilization.

Objective: The objective of the study is to assess the patient's satisfaction with neurosurgery outpatient department (OPD) services at Dear Ghazi Khan Medical College, Dear Ghazi Khan.

Study design & setting: This hospital based cross sectional study was conducted in Neurosurgery outpatient department of Ghazi khan Medical College, Dear Ghazi Khan.

Methods: Data was collected using preformed, pretested questionnaire from 326 patients. Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 21. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for qualitative variables and dimensions of satisfaction. Chi-square test was applied to assess the statistical relation between the defined dependent and independent variables. P value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results: The proportion of patients having very good level of satisfaction was 27.3% while 17.2% had satisfactory level of satisfaction. Satisfaction of the respondents was not significantly associated with age of the respondents ($p=0.383$) Variables including respondent's education ($p=0.008$), gender of the respondents ($p=0.000$) and monthly family income ($p=0.021$) were significantly associated with patient's satisfaction.

Conclusion: The study findings conclude that education, gender and monthly family income are key determinants of patient's satisfaction with healthcare services.

Key Words: Patient satisfaction, Neurosurgery, service quality.

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INTRODUCTION:

The ultimate goals of healthcare system are to provide quality healthcare services, fair financing and responsiveness.¹ The quality healthcare services are safe, efficient, patient centered, timely, equitable and effective. The quality of healthcare services may be defined subjectively or objectively. Objectively the quality means conformance with the standards while subjectively the quality healthcare services are those which meet or exceeds the patient expectations.² The measurement of patient's satisfaction with the services is complex and multidimensional because it is solely a subjective phenomenon which is dependent on several factors like patient sociodemographic factors, lifestyle, physical & mental health. The findings obtained from satisfaction survey are highly influenced by the selected population the timing of the interview, the type of tool used to collect the data and the methodology of the survey. The results of patient satisfaction surveys should be interpreted in accordance with social circumstances.³ Improvement in socioeconomic status, literacy level and development of private sector hospitals network in developing countries healthcare services has been established as consumer driven entity and patient satisfaction with the services is the indicator for assessing the state of current healthcare system. The perceived needs of the patients, expectations from the system and healthcare provider and healthcare experiences are embodied in the patient satisfaction with services. Primary stakeholders of healthcare system are the patients and relative to the past users of healthcare are more knowledgeable and informed, hence demand valid and accurate evidence of healthcare quality.^{4,5}

The literature review revealed that the concept of patient satisfaction is multifactorial and complex.

There are many universally acceptable definitions of patient satisfaction. Donabedian the famous personality of healthcare quality theory proposed that to ensure the patient satisfaction the instrumental role is played by interpersonal process of care. The satisfaction of the patient with healthcare services is also influenced by the beliefs, values and prior expectations. According to world health organization the interlinking relationship between perceived needs, patient expectations and experiences determine the satisfaction with the healthcare services. For determining the effectiveness, quality of healthcare delivery and areas of weaknesses within healthcare system the useful tool is patient satisfaction.^{6,7}

Studies revealed that patient satisfaction with healthcare services are more willing to seek medical advice, Compliance with treatment is enhanced and also refer patients to their medical practitioner. Research conducted in by Sharma *et al* revealed that patient satisfaction research serves as a mean of holding physicians accountable. The competitive environment in medical field has pushed the hospitals to strive for satisfying the patients requirements. Internationally the ranking of healthcare institutions is done on the basis of service quality, patient retention, decreased expenditure, enhanced profitability and customer satisfaction.⁸ This study was designed to assess the patient satisfaction with neurosurgery outpatient department (OPD) services of Ghazi Khan Teaching Hospital, Dear Ghazi Khan.

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of the study is to assess the patient's satisfaction with neurosurgery outpatient department (OPD) services at Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College, Dera Ghazi Khan.

METHODOLOGY

This hospital based descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out at neurosurgery outpatient department of Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College, Dera Ghazi Khan from July 2018 to December 2018 after taking approval from Institutional ethical review committee. Sample size was calculated for the study at 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error and 68.7%⁹ anticipated population proportion (Satisfaction level) was 326. Non probability consecutive sampling technique was used to select the study subjects. A preformed, pretested and structured questionnaire was used to collect the relevant information from the study participants. The questionnaire comprises of two domains. The first domain contains socio demographic profile and the second domain contains study variables. The patients were explained the purpose of the study and items of the questionnaire were discussed for clarification and were assured that data will only be used for the purpose of research and confidentiality of the data would be completely secured. Data was collected from the respondents after obtaining informed consent. Data was entered and analyzed by using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21. Total 16 questions were asked to measure satisfaction of the respondents with the services. Response of each question was measured on a 5 points Likert Scale, strongly disagree = 1, disagree = 2, uncertain = 3, agree = 4, and strongly agree = 5. The composite score of each respondent ranges from 16-80. The level of satisfaction on the basis of composite score was divided into three categories, the score ≥ 65 was categorized as very good, the score with range 50-64 was categorized as satisfactory and score ≤ 35 was taken as poor. Descriptive analysis was done and mean and standard deviation was calculated for quantitative variables like age. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for qualitative variables i.e. patient's education, monthly family income, Stratification was done according to age, patient's educational status and monthly family income. Chi square test was applied to assess the statistical relation between the defined dependent and independent variables. P value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

A total 326 patients visiting the neurosurgery outpatient department were enrolled in the study. The mean age of respondents was 26.48 ± 6.25 years. The age distribution of the respondents (n=326) showed that the highest proportion of women were between the ages of 21-25 years (35.6%), followed by 26-30 years (25.8%) and 15-20 years (16.9%) and 31-35 years (15.9%). The educational status of the respondents showed that 23.9% of them were unable to read and write while 45.7% had primary schooling and only 9.6% had above secondary education. The information provided by the respondents regarding their monthly family income showed that 83.5% of the families had monthly income below RS. 50,000 while 16.5% were earning more than RS. 50,000.

The stratification of level of satisfaction with services in relation to the age distribution of the respondents depicted that the highest proportion (29.2%) with very good level of satisfaction was in age group of 21-25 years, similarly 41.9% respondents with good level of satisfaction with services was also between 21-23 years age group. Satisfactory level of satisfaction was noted 32.1% each in 21-25 years and 26-30 years age groups. The majority of respondents (34.2%) with poor level of satisfaction was in the age group of 26-30 years. The difference in level of satisfaction with services in various age groups was not significant ($p=0.383$). The cross tabulation of respondent's educational level and satisfaction with services showed that among patients with very good level of satisfaction 46.1% had primary education and 29.2% had secondary and above level of education while 65.8% having poor satisfaction with services had primary education. The satisfaction with services was found to be significantly associated with educational level of the respondents ($p=0.008$).

The monthly family income and satisfaction with services showed that the monthly family income of 84.3% women with very good level of satisfaction was below 50,000 and 13.2% respondents with poor satisfaction level had family income $\geq 50,000$. Family income was significantly associated with neurosurgery outpatient department services satisfaction ($p=0.021$).

Table I: Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents (n=326)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
15-25	55	16.9%
26-35	116	35.6%
36-45	84	25.8%
46-55	52	15.9%
≥56	19	05.8%
Gender		
Male	255	78.2%
Female	71	21.8%
Education		
Unable to read & write	28	23.9%
Primary	149	45.7%
Up to Secondary	68	20.8%
Above Secondary	31	09.6%
Monthly income		
<50,000	272	83.5%
≥50,000	54	16.5%

Table II: Patient's satisfaction with obstetric services (n=326)

Patient satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Very good	89	27.3%
Good	143	43.9%
Satisfactory	56	17.2%
Poor	38	11.6%
Total	326	100%

Table III: Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents and satisfaction with services

Sociodemographic characteristics	Satisfaction level with services				P value
	V. Good	Good	Satisfactory	Poor	
Age					0.383
15-25	16 (18.0%)	22 (15.4%)	10 (17.9%)	07 (18.4%)	
26-35	26 (29.2%)	60 (41.9%)	18 (32.1%)	12 (31.6%)	
36-45	20 (22.5%)	33 (23.1%)	18 (32.1%)	13 (34.2%)	
46-55	19 (21.3%)	23 (16.1%)	07 (12.5%)	03 (07.9%)	
≥56	08 (09.0%)	05 (03.5%)	03 (05.4%)	03 (07.9%)	
Total	89 (100%)	143 (100%)	56 (100%)	38 (100%)	
Gender					0.000
Male	80 (89.9%)	139 (97.2%)	29 (51.8%)	07 (18.4%)	
Female	09 (10.1%)	04 (02.8%)	27 (48.2%)	31 (81.6%)	
Total	89 (100%)	143 (100%)	56 (100%)	38 (100%)	
Education					0.008
Unable to read & write	22 (24.7%)	40 (28.0%)	10 (17.8%)	06 (15.8%)	
Primary	41 (46.1%)	60 (42.0%)	23 (41.1%)	25 (65.8%)	
Up to Secondary	12 (13.5%)	30 (21.0%)	20 (35.7%)	06 (15.8%)	
Above Secondary	14 (15.7%)	13 (09.0%)	03 (05.4%)	01 (02.6%)	
Total	89 (100%)	143 (100%)	56 (100%)	38 (100%)	
Monthly income					0.021
<50,000	75 (84.3%)	125 (87.4%)	37 (69.6%)	33 (86.8%)	
≥50,000	14 15.7%	18 (12.6%)	17 (30.4%)	05 (13.2%)	
Total	89 (100%)	143 (100%)	56 (100%)	38 (100%)	

DISCUSSION:

Patient satisfaction is important component of the quality healthcare services. Healthcare services can't be reserved for future use and many factors determine the satisfaction level of the patient with services. For provision of quality healthcare services and facilitate the management measurement of patients' satisfaction level is compulsory. The present study assessed the level of patient's satisfaction with neurosurgery outpatient department (OPD) services. The recent years has witnessed that measurement of patient satisfaction both in private, and public health care institutions is gaining momentum, and studies on measurement tools of patient satisfaction are becoming more prevalent. Our study findings showed that majority of the respondents has either very good or good level of satisfaction with the services which are consistent with the findings of Vural F et al. in which major proportion of patients was very much satisfied with health care services of hospital.⁹ These higher levels of patient satisfaction might be at partially attributed to the fact that Neurosurgery Department of Ghazi Khan teaching Hospital is the only hospital in Division without any competing health care institution.

The findings of the study revealed that no considerably significant difference was noted with age and patient satisfaction (0.383), it was observed that older age patients were relatively more satisfied than their counterparts. These findings are consistent with the results of Bener A et al.¹⁰ The findings are contrary to Japipaul study in which greatest level of satisfaction was in the group 15-24 years old, and then it decreased gradually and increased again in the group who were over 60 years old.¹¹

Of the studied patients, 78.2% were males and 21.8% were females. Male patients were more satisfied with the outpatient department services as compared to females. A statistically significant difference was observed between male and female patients in terms of level of satisfaction ($P = 0.000$) which is similar to the findings of Bener A et al. in which male patients were more satisfied with the services.¹⁰ The results of this present study revealed that patient satisfaction with services increased as the educational level of the respondents increased and difference in satisfaction level of the respondents with variable educational backgrounds was statistically significant (0.008) which is consistent with the findings of Afzal M et al. in which mean percent satisfaction score was higher in patients who had educational level of intermediate and above as compared to the patients who were in under matric category of education and lowest satisfaction level.¹²

The health system of the country should be devised in a way which escalate client satisfaction with health care organizations by formulating policies through which customer friendly services can be provided. The hospital administrators must endeavor to model hospital more comfortable and agreeable for the patients. Health care professionals and staff ought to comprehend patient's expectations from the facility, take priority over the factors leading to lower satisfaction related to care, and should put the maximal efforts to meet the standards of care and dispense care that is consonant with their expectations. Sensitizing the staff by educating them on communication and interpersonal relationship and stress management might be a prudent step to upgrade satisfaction level. There is an imperative need to effectively communicate with patients regarding their health status, listening to their concerns which helps in subsiding their anxiety and developing their confidence in health system. The working hours of the health care professionals should be decreased to increase their productivity as well as it is equally important to avoid continuous working shifts for doctors. The number of doctors, allied health professionals, paramedics should be increased in hospitals to upraise patient satisfaction.^{13, 14, 15}

CONCLUSION:

The study findings conclude that education, gender and monthly family income are key determinants of patient's satisfaction with healthcare services.

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